

Studies on some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complexes. Part VI. Investigation on the Ferrocyanogen Complexes of Cu(I), Ti(III and IV), Cr(II), and Mn(III) in the Light of Redox Potential

Wahid U. Malik

The ferrocyanogen complex of Cu (I), Ti (III), Ti (IV), Cr (II), and Mn (III) have been studied by amperometry. The results have been interpreted in the light of the oxidation-reduction potential existing in the reactions between Cu(I), Ti(III) or Cr(II) and potassium ferricyanide and that between Mn (III) and potassium ferrocyanide. The composition of cuprous ferrocyanide (white in colour) has been found to be $K_2Cu^I Fe^II Cy_6$, whereas the products obtained by interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide may be represented by the formula $K_2Cu^{II} Fe^{II} Cy_6$ and $KCu_2^I Fe^{II} Cy_6$. The titanium complexes of the following compositions have been obtained: $KTi^{III} Fe^{II} Cy_6$; $Ti_4^{III} (Fe^{II} Cy_6)_3$; $Ti^{IV} Fe^{II} Cy_6$ (for titanous chloride-potassium ferricyanide reaction). For the chromous chloride—potassium ferricyanide reaction complexes of the type $Cr_3^{II} (Fe^{III} Cy_6)_2$ and $K_2Cr^{II} Fe^{II} Cy_6$ are obtained depending on the mode of mixing of the reactants.

The Mn (III)—potassium ferrocyanide reaction, besides providing evidence of the existence of the redox potential in the system:

also shows the presence of the complex anion $Mn(SO_4)^{2-}$ in the reaction mixture. The latter fact is also supported from the amperometric titrations between Mn (III) and potassium ferricyanide. The various complexes formed are $Mn^{III} Fe^{III} Cy_6$, $KMn^{III} Fe^{II} Cy_6$; and $Mn^{III} Fe^{III} Cy_6$ (for the Mn^{III} —ferricyanide reaction).

The problem of the existence of redox potential in the system comprising the interaction of metal ions and alkali ferro- and ferricyanides has attracted little attention of the workers in this field. Attention to this fact was first drawn by Davidson (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1937, 14, 238, 277), who on the basis of some preliminary experiments demonstrated the influence of the redox potential in the system:

on the formation of Prussian blue. Since then nothing has been done to record such influences by investigating the composition of metal ferrocyanogen complexes.

Of the many metal ions, which could be studied from this aspect, a few typical ones, namely Cu(I), Ti(III and IV), Cr(II), and Mn (III) were selected for the present investigations.

Preliminary experiments, performed on mixing varying proportions of equimolecular solutions of cuprous chloride and potassium ferrocyanide showed, that the precipitate obtained with an excess of the latter reactant was reddish brown in colour, whereas that obtained in presence of excess of cuprous chloride was white. Also with excess of potassium ferrocyanide the supernatant liquid turned to green and finally to blue due to the probable formation of Prussian blue by slow decomposition of hydroferrocyanic acid. As for the interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide, brown-coloured compounds were obtained in all cases, irrespective of the excess of either of the reactants although with excess of ferricyanide, the colour was quite dark, approaching to black. Here also the supernatant liquid turned green on keeping.

In the case of Ti(III)—potassium ferrocyanide reaction, a dark yellow precipitate was

obtained with the excess of titanous ions whereas with an equimolecular proportion of the reactants and with excess of potassium ferrocyanide, an orange-coloured precipitate was obtained. Further, in test tubes containing large excess of potassium ferrocyanide, a blue colour developed on the surface of the precipitate on keeping. For Ti(III) and potassium ferricyanide interaction, an orange-coloured precipitate (similar to that of titanous ferrocyanide) was obtained with excess of the former, but for mixtures containing equimolecular proportions of the reactants or excess of potassium ferricyanide, a dark brown precipitate was obtained. Ti(IV) does not give any precipitate with potassium ferricyanide in the cold and on heating only a slight yellow turbidity appears. It, however, reacts with potassium ferrocyanide. Here too the colour of the precipitate depended on the proportion of the reactants mixed. With excess of titanous ions, a chocolate-coloured precipitate was obtained, whereas on mixing equimolecular proportion of the reactants a dark brown precipitate was formed. Addition of excess of potassium ferrocyanide resulted in the formation of a yellowish brown precipitate.

The interaction of Cr(II) with potassium ferro- and ferrocyanides remained obscure so far. The Cr(II)—ferrocyanide reaction was first studied in our laboratory (Malik and Abubacker, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1959, **301**, 343, 350). These studies were further extended so as to include the interaction of Cr(II) and potassium ferricyanide. The reaction product was dirty yellow with excess of ferricyanide, but it was yellowish green with chromous chloride.

The reaction between Mn(III) and alkali ferro- and ferricyanides has hitherto not been investigated and presents a number of complexities. The manganic ion, unlike Cu(I), Cr(II), Ti(III), etc., is fairly unstable in the aqueous solution and changes of the type:

are known to take place in solution. Further, the possibility of the reaction $2\text{Mn}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Mn}^{2+} + \text{Mn}^{4+}$ cannot be ruled out. Stability is usually obtained by changing the simple manganic ion into the orthophosphate, potassium manganicyanide and the alums. It is also observed that if the oxidation of Mn(II) is carried out in concentrated hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid solutions, it does not contain pure Mn(III), but is mixed with chloro-complexes of intermediate composition (Ibers and Davidson, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4744) or the sulphato-complexes of the type $\text{Mn}(\text{SO}_4)_2^-$ (Ubbelohde, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 1605). Mn(III) solution, prepared by the method recommended by Ubbelohde, was, however, used to study the ferrocyanogen complexes in spite of the limitations encountered in obtaining a pure manganic sulphate solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cuprous chloride was obtained by reducing cupric chloride by copper turnings in presence of HCl (conc.). To the colorless solution, thus obtained, excess of water was added to form the white precipitate. It was washed with ethanol and then with ether, and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator over lime. The solution was prepared by dissolving 1.98 g. of the dried substance in 100 c.c. 0.1*N*-KCl solution. It was kept under a layer of paraffin to avoid oxidation. The strength of the solution was determined by titrating against 0.1*M* ammonium thiocyanate, using ferric alum as the indicator (Malik *et al.*, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1959, **299**, 322). The strength was found to be 0.098*M*.

To a 12.5% titanous chloride solution (250 c.c.) in 15% HCl (B.D.H., 2g.) spectroscopically pure titanium metal was added. Hydrochloric acid gas was then passed in the solution for about 10 minutes. The mixture was heated to dissolve the titanium metal.

HCl gas was then passed for about an hour while keeping the solution in a freezing mixture. On keeping for some time, violet crystals of titanous chloride appeared. The crystals were washed with air-free double distilled water and dissolved in 15% HCl solution (these were also found to be soluble in absolute ethanol). The strength was determined by titrating against 0.1*N*-KMnO₄ (Scott, "Standard Methods of Analysis", 5th ed., p. 984). The strength was found to be 0.087*M*.

12.5% TiCl₄ in 15% hydrochloric acid (B.D.H.) was employed for preparing the solution. The strength was determined by precipitating titanium as hydroxide and weighing as TiO₂ (Scott, *loc. cit.*, p. 982). The strength was found to be 0.093*M*.

Chromous chloride solution was obtained after reducing chromic chloride with zinc and HCl. The method recommended by Balth and Baeler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1474) with a slight modification was followed (Malik and Abubacker, *loc. cit.*). The solution was stored in a Stone-type bottle (Stone, *Anal. Chem.*, 1948, 20, 747) and it remained stable for many weeks. Since the strength of chromous chloride had to be determined and checked occasionally during the course of experiments, the method of Zintl and Rienacker (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 161, 374, 385; 1927, 168, 97), using copper sulphate or potassium dichromate, was replaced by a quicker method. 0.1*N*-KMnO₄ (50c.c.), acidified with 2*N*-H₂SO₄ (15c.c.) was taken in a 100 c.c. beaker and covered with a layer (about 0.5c.c. thick) of kerosine. A chromous chloride solution (2c.c.) was then transferred to the permanganate, keeping the tip of the burette under the layer of kerosine. The mixture was stirred and kept aside for 5 minutes to ensure complete oxidation of Cr(II) and the excess of permanganate titrated against 0.1*N* ferrous ammonium sulphate using a Tinsley potentiometer (type 387B). The strength of chromous chloride then determined was 0.245*N*.

The manganic sulphate solution was prepared by the method recommended by Ubbelohde (*loc. cit.*) to avoid formation of higher oxides in the solution. It was found safer to add a little more sulphuric acid than that recommended by Ubbelohde. Attempts to prepare solutions of higher concentrations than 0.07*N* met with failure. The strength was determined by titrating against ferrous ammonium sulphate of known strength. The end point was detected by the change in colour from light green to yellowish green. It was further confirmed by titrating potentiometrically against hydrogen peroxide. A jump in potential of 0.35 volt was observed at the end point by the addition of a single drop of the titrant.

The potassium ferro- and ferricyanide solutions were prepared and stored as described in Part V (this *issue*, p. 297). Their strength was determined by titrating against potassium permanganate (for the ferrocyanide) and iodometrically (for the ferricyanide).

Amperometric Titrations

Polarographic measurements were carried out with a Fischer electrode in conjunction with a Multiflex galvanometer of type MGF2 (sensitivity, 1: 10; 4×10^{-9} ampere per division) against a S.C.E. 0.1*M*-KCl [(4*N*-HCl for Ti(III)] and CaCl₂ in HCl for Ti(IV) were used as the supporting electrolyte and gelatin (0.01%) as the maximum suppressor. For studying the manganic sulphate reaction, the sulphuric acid present in the solution was enough to be used as the supporting electrolyte. Purified nitrogen gas was passed in the cell for maintaining an inert atmosphere. Before carrying out the titration, polarograms for the reduction of various metal ions were taken for the following mixtures:

(i)	0.8c.c. of 0.098 <i>M</i> -Cu ₂ Cl ₂	+1c.c. gelatin	+18.4c.c. of 0.1 <i>M</i> -KCl.
(ii)	0.8c.c. of 0.087 <i>M</i> -TiCl ₃	+ Do	+18.4 of 4 <i>N</i> -HCl
(iii)	0.8c.c. of 0.093 <i>M</i> -TiCl ₄	+ Do	+18.4 of CaCl ₂ in HCl
(iv)	0.5c.c. of 0.245 <i>M</i> -CrCl ₂	+ Do	+18.5 of 0.1 <i>M</i> -KCl.
(v)	10c.c. of 0.068 <i>M</i> -Mn ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	+ Do	+11c.c. water,

The E_1 values from the curves were found to be 0.23V (Cu_2Cl_2), 0.12V (TiCl_3), 0.14V (TiCl_4), and 1.51V [$\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$]. For Cr(II) the anodic wave was not reversible.

The potentials to be applied for the amperometric titrations were found from the plateau of the polarograms. These were: 0.6V (Cu_2Cl_2), 0.4V (TiCl_4), 0.2V (CrCl_2), 0.4V $\text{Mn}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$. For Ti (III), titrations were carried out at 0.0 volt. The latter potential was also applied in the case of Cu(I)— K_3FeCy_6 titrations.

The results are summarised in the following tables. A few typical amperometric titration curves are depicted in Figs. 1 to 5.

TABLE I

Cu(I)—ferrocyanide reaction.

Potential applied = 0.6 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. in the cell. 0.098M- Cu_2Cl_2 .	Vol. from the curves. 0.1M- K_4FeCy_6 .	Ratio at the inflection point. $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2 : \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$.
0.2 c.c.	0.2 c.c.	1:1
0.4	0.4	1:1
0.6	0.6	1:1
0.1M- K_4FeCy_6 .	0.098M- Cu_2Cl_2 .	
0.2 c.c.	0.22 c.c.	1:1
0.4	0.39	1:1
0.6	0.61	1:1

TABLE II

Cu(I)—ferricyanide reaction.

Potential applied = 0.0 volt. and 0.6 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

*Vol. in the cell. 0.098M- Cu_2Cl_2 .	Vol. from the curves. 0.155M- K_3FeCy_6 .		Ratio at the inflection point. $\text{Cu}_2\text{Cl}_2 : \text{K}_3\text{FeCy}_6$.	
	0.0 volt.	0.6 volt.	0.0 volt.	0.6 volt.
0.2 c.c.	0.25 c.c.	0.1, 0.25c.c.	1:1.8	1:1;1:2
0.4	0.50	0.30, 0.60	1:2.0	1:0.9;1:1.94
0.5	0.60	0.39, 0.72	1:1.9	1:1; 1:1.90

* 0.2 c.c., 0.5 c.c. and 0.6 c.c. taken when applying 0.6 volt.

0.155M- K_3FeCy_6 .	0.098M- Cu_2Cl_2 .			
	0.0 volt.	0.6 volt.		
0.2 c.c.	0.15 c.c.	0.15, 0.28 c.c.	1:2.1	1:2.1:1
0.4	0.30	0.3, 0.60	1:2.1	1:2.1;1:1.15
0.6	0.50	0.52, 0.82	1:1.9	1:1.8;1:1.16

TABLE III

Ti(III)—ferrocyanide reaction.

Potential applied = 0.0 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. in the cell. 0.087M- TiCl_3 .	Vol. from the curves. 0.1M- K_4FeCy_6 .	Ratio at the inflection point. $\text{TiCl}_3 : \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$.
0.3c.c.	0.22c.c.	1.0 : 0.85
0.6	0.42	1.0 : 0.80
1.0	0.65	1.0 : 0.75
0.1M- K_4FeCy_6 .	0.0875 M- TiCl_3 .	
0.3 c.c.	0.34 c.c.	1:1
0.6	0.70	1:1
1.0	1.18	1:1

TABLE IV

*Ti(IV)-ferricyanide reaction.*Potential applied = 0.4 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. in the cell.	Vol. from the curves.	Ratio at the inflection point.
0.087M-TiCl ₃ .	0.155M-K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	TiCl ₃ : K ₃ FeCy ₆ .
0.3c.c.	0.20c.c.	1:1.20
0.8	0.35	1:1.04
1.0	0.05	1:1.00
0.155M-K ₃ FeCy ₆	0.087M-TiCl ₃ .	
0.4	0.66	1:1.2
1.0	1.9	1:1.0

TABLE V

*Ti(IV)-ferrocyanide reaction.*Potential applied = 0.4 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. in the cell.	Vol. from the curves.	Ratio at the inflection point.
0.093M-TiCl ₄ .	0.01M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	TiCl ₄ : K ₄ FeCy ₆ .
0.3c.c.	No definite break	
0.0	0.6c.c.	1:1.1
1.0	0.9	1:1.0
0.1M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	0.093M-TiCl ₄ .	
0.4	0.4	1:1.07
0.6	0.6	1:1.07
1.0	1.1	1:1.00

TABLE VI

*Cr(II)-ferricyanide reaction.*Potential applied = 0.2 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. in the cell.	Vol. from the curves.	Ratio at the inflection point.
0.245M-CrCl ₂ .	0.1M-K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	CrCl ₂ : K ₃ FeCy ₆ .
0.4c.c.	0.46c.c.	2.04:1
0.8	0.90	2.04:1
1.2	1.45	2.02:1
0.1M-K ₃ FeCy ₆ .	0.245M-CrCl ₂ .	
0.5	0.30	1.47:1
1.0	0.55	1.35:1
1.5	0.95	1.59:1

TABLE VII

*Mn(III)-ferrocyanide reaction.*Potential applied = 0.4 volt. Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Vol. and conc. in the cell.	Vol. from the curves.	Ratio at the inflection point.
Mn(III).	0.2M-K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	Mn ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ .
20c.c. 0.0243 M	1.24 c.c.	1:1
20 0.016	0.80	1:1
20 0.020	1.00	1:1
K ₄ FeCy ₆ .	0.04M-Mn(III).	
20 c.c. 0.002	2.5 c.c.	2.05:1
20 0.0025	2.6	2.06:1
20 0.0030	3.0	2.06:1

TABLE VIII.

Mn (III)-ferricyanide reaction.

Potential applied = 0.4 volt. Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°

Vol. and conc. of Mn (III) in the cell.	Vol. of 0.2M·K ₃ FeCy ₆ from the curves.	Ratio at the inflection point, Mn ³⁺ : FeCy ₆ ³⁻
20 c.c. ; 0.0133M	1.3 c.c.	1:1
20 ; 0.0106	1.7	1.02:1
20 ; 0.0200	2.0	1:1

DISCUSSION

Cu (I) *Ferro- and Ferricyanides*

For the interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferrocyanide, the combining ratio of the reactants comes out to be 1:1, thereby pointing towards the formation of the complex K₂Cu₂^IFe^{III}Cy₆ (white in colour).

The interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide presents a number of interesting features. Considering the oxidation potentials of the systems:

the equilibrium constant of the reaction:

It would mean that during the interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide, a considerably large amount of cuprous chloride is oxidised to the cupric state and consequently the ferricyanide is reduced to the ferrocyanide. Under these conditions the reaction would be:

The overall reaction would be

FIG. 1. Curves 1-0.2 c.c. 2-0.4 c.c. and 3-0.6 c.c. of 0.155M·K₃FeCy₆ in the cell.

Results on amperometric titrations support the above mechanism, where a ratio Cu₂Cl₂: K₃FeCy₆ as 1:2 for both reverse and direct titrations, carried out at 0.0 and 0.6 volt, is obtained. A ratio of 1:1 is also obtained for the second break from the curve at 0.6 volt. From this it may be concluded that some of the cuprous chloride reacts with potassium ferricyanide to give cuprous ferricyanide:

It therefore amounts to the fact that the reaction between cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide is not simply an oxidation-reduction but proceeds with the formation of cupric ferrocyanide together with a little amount of cuprous ferricyanide. Incidentally, the reaction is just the reverse of that for the formation of Prussian blue, where the equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is of the order 10^5 and that the formation of ferric ferrocyanide is a slow reaction.

Further confirmation for this reaction between potassium ferricyanide and cuprous chloride was sought for carrying out the amperometric titrations between cupric chloride and potassium ferro- and ferricyanides. Here it was found that the ratio $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot \text{K}_4\text{FeCy}_6$ or K_3FeCy_6 is 3:2. For this ratio, the composition of cupric ferrocyanide would be $\text{Cu}_3^{II}(\text{Fe}^{III}\text{Cy}_6)_2$. Formation of a compound with this composition is, however, not met with when considering the interaction of cuprous chloride and potassium ferricyanide.

Ti(III and IV) Ferro- and Ferricyanides

The reverse titrations give a ratio 1:1 for the reactants, pointing towards the formation of the complex titanous ferrocyanide of composition $\text{KTi}^{III}\text{Fe}^{II}\text{Cy}_6$. For the direct titrations concordant values are not obtained, but these may be approximated to 1:0.75. Here the composition of the complex would be $\text{Ti}_4^{III}(\text{Fe}^{II}\text{Cy}_6)_3$ according to the stoichiometric equation:

FIG. 2. Curves (1) 0.3 c.c., (2) 0.6 c.c. and (3) 1.0 c.c. of 0.1M-K₄FeCy₆ in the cell.

That the composition of the complex formed by the interaction of titanous chloride and potassium ferricyanide can be simply represented by $\text{Ti}^{III}\text{Fe}^{III}\text{Cy}_6$ ($\text{Ti}^{3+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{3-}$ as 1:1) appears to be highly improbable in view of the oxidation potentials existing in the system. The potential values of $\text{FeCy}_6^{4-} \rightleftharpoons \text{FeCy}_6^{3-} + e$ and $\text{Ti}^{3+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Ti}^{4+} + e$ are -0.44V and -0.6V respectively. The equilibrium constant of the reaction:

would be 2.7×10^6 .

The large value of K in this case also points towards the fact that the titanous ions are oxidised to titanous ions during the course of the reaction and $\text{Ti}^{IV}\text{Fe}^{II}\text{Cy}_6$ is formed. The formation of this complex would be a ratio 1:1 for the reactants and this is what has been obtained from the amperometric titrations. It appears that the reaction takes place in two stages:

FIG. 3. Curves (1) 0.4 c.c., (2) 0.6 c.c., (3) 1.0 c.c. of 0.1M-K₄FeCy₆ in the cell.

The view that titanous ferrocyanide is formed by the interaction of titanous chloride and potassium ferricyanide finds support in the titration between potassium ferrocyanide and titanous chloride. The ratio for the interaction of the two reactants again comes out to be 1:1, providing a definite proof for the formation of the complex $\text{Ti}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$.

Cr(II)-Ferricyanide

The insoluble complex (yellowish green in colour), formed by the interaction of chromous chloride and potassium ferricyanide may, take place according to the stoichiometric equations:

The results of the reverse amperometric titrations point towards the formation of the complex $\text{Cr}_3^{\text{II}}(\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6)_2$ ($\text{Cr}^{2+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{3-}$ as 3:2 approx.). No clue regarding the existence of complex $\text{KCr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$, however, is forthcoming on the basis of amperometric titrations.

FIG. 4. Curves (1) 0.5 c.c., (2) 1.0 c.c., (3) 1.5 c.c. of 0.1M-K₃FeCy₆ in the cell

This reaction is also worth considering from the viewpoint of redox potential existing in the system. The equilibrium constant of the reaction:

is 2.5×10^{14} ($\text{FeCy}_6^{4-} \rightleftharpoons \text{FeCy}_6^{3-} + e = -0.44\text{V}$; $\text{Cr}^{2+} \rightleftharpoons \text{Cr}^{3+} + e = 0.41\text{V}$).

It would mean that during the interaction of chromous chloride and potassium ferricyanide a considerably large amount of chromous chloride would be oxidised to chromic state and the ferricyanide is reduced to the ferrocyanide. Due to the existence of

oxidation-reduction potential in the reaction, the following reactions may be expected to take place:

Of these the last reaction is quite slow at the ordinary temperature. The faster reaction between chromous chloride and potassium ferrocyanide (so also between chromous chloride and potassium ferricyanide) is more likely to occur. The first three reactions point towards the formation of complexes $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$ and $\text{Cr}_2^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$ and these could be formed when the reactants are mixed in the ratios $\text{Cr}^{2+} : \text{FeCy}_6^{3-}$ as 2:1 and 3:1 respectively. The results on direct amperometric titrations give evidence for the complex having the formula $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}^{\text{II}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$.

Mn(III)—Ferro- and Ferricyanides

The possible reaction between manganic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide may be represented as follows:

followed by either

FIG. 5. Curves (1) 4 c.c., (2) 0.8 c.c., and (3) 9.6 c.c. of 0.05M Mn(III) in the cell.

The reactions (i) and (ii) would take place when manganic sulphate and potassium ferrocyanide combine in the ratio 2:3 and 1:2 respectively, whereas reactions (iii) and (iv) combined would give the ratio 1:1 and (iii) and (v) combined would give the ratio 1:2.

The amperometric titrations, when carried out with Mn(III) in the cell, give a ratio 1:1, pointing towards the formation of the complex $Mn^{II}Fe^{II}Cy_6$, the overall reaction taking place being

(equations *iii* and *iv* combined).

Here again, the evidence of the existence of oxidation-reduction potential for the reaction:

is forthcoming. The large value of

$$K = \frac{Mn^{2+} \times FeCy_6^{3-}}{Mn^{3+} \times FeCy_6^{4-}} = 3.09 \times 10^7$$

point towards the possibility of Mn(III) being reduced to Mn(II) and the ferrocyanide oxidised to the ferricyanide during the course of the reaction (in fact, the reaction for the formation of manganic ferrocyanide would be a much slower process than the formation of ferric ferrocyanide). The amperometric titrations, however, failed to supply any information regarding the formation of the complex $2KMn^{II}Fe^{III}Cy_6$ since the potential applied for these titrations could give an idea of the reaction taking place with Mn(III) only.

Reverse titrations give the ratio Mn^{3+} to $FeCy_6^{4-}$ as 2:1. The combining ratio does not fit any of the mentioned reactions. The probable reaction for this may be

Although the reaction brings out indirectly one important fact, namely, the confirmation regarding the existence of the complex anion $Mn(SO_4)_2^-$ in the manganic solution (Ubbelohde, *loc. cit.*), it is rather difficult to visualise the possibility of such a reaction taking place in view of the oxidation potential existing in the system under investigation.

From the amperometric titrations between Mn(III) and potassium ferricyanide, the combining ratio comes out to be 1:1. Here again, the proof for the presence of the complex anion $Mn(SO_4)_2^-$ is forthcoming since the only possibility of the formation of the insoluble complex can be according to the reaction:

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